

A STUDY ON DEVELOPING ENGLISH LANGUAGE USING SMART PHONES AMONG UNDER GRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract

This study is intended to explore ways for developing English Language using smart phones in students' daily life. Usage of smart phones has been increased among the youth in this modern world. It is the need of hour to grab the situation and utilize to develop English language using smart phones among the under graduate students. Students develop their LSRW skills by using mobile phones. They are accustomed to use mobile phones to message, chat, for social sites and searching for the information what they don't have an idea. Nowadays mobile phones are used extensively for getting information as they are handy and convenient to use. Sometimes students use mobiles for their preparation of examinations. There is another side also where it has been misused. It depends on solely on the discretion of the students. This study reveals how the students are using mobile phones, apps installed in students' mobile phones for developing language skills, the usage of English language in social sites, impact of swayam course in developing English language.

Keywords: Language Skills – smart phones – Apps – Social sites – online dictionary – swayam courses

Introduction

Literature is the miniature of the world. It reflects the society and guides the young learners in a positive way. It provides pleasure and instruction. Various literary materials are included to develop English Language. At undergraduate level, text book is the primary material for developing English Language.

English language is developed through literature. Graded literature is presented in textbooks to improve the four skills of the language. In the modern world students use not only textbooks for learning the language but also depend upon other materials such as newspapers, short stories, novels and mobile phones to develop their language.

Mobiles phones are used extensively in the modern world. We can't imagine majority of the youth not having mobile phones. It is the need of an hour to make the youth realize the importance of mobiles for learning the language. Generally mobiles are used for

- Communication
- Newspaper reading
- Online dictionary

- Audio books
- Apps
- Recording their own speech
- Swayam courses

The primary function and use of the mobile is to communicate. The advent of mobile has changed the world drastically. People depend excessively upon mobile for communication. Generally communication takes place in mother tongue over a phone. Communication in mother over a phone is an easy process. People find comfortable to exchange their ideas. Learners are encouraged to talk in English over a phone. Initially it is difficult as there is an absence of sign language. Learners are to be trained to learn the mobile communication jargon so that, they are able to communicate well over a phone. It is said that majority of the learners' language has been improved.

“An ideal society should be mobile, should be full of channels for conveying a change taking place in one part to other parts. In an ideal society, there should be many interests consciously communicated and shared”- By B.R.Ambedkar (<https://www.brainyquote.com>)

Various messenger tools are available in mobile phones. Mobiles are used to send SMS, Whatsapp and other messengers apps to send the messages. Generally the youth may send messages in their mother tongue. Messenger tools in the mobile should be recognized as an important tool to develop the language. Learners are instructed to send the messages in English so that, their language can be improved.

Some types of learning through Mobile phones are pointed out

- Learning through sound
- Learning through sound
- Learning through text messages
- Learning through a graphical display
- Learning information obtained from data internet search
- Learning through cameras and videos

(The Role of Mobile Phones in Education and Instruction of classroom materials)

Every mobile phone has recording facility. Learners are encouraged to record their talk. Later it will be analyzed and improved. It is a great source to understand their own speech. Finally it helps to improve pronunciation of the learners.

“Ipadio lets you record upto 60 minutes of high quality audio. You can then add titles, descriptions, images, and geo-locate your recordings before instantly uploading to your ipadio.com or cross-post to your Twitter, facebook or blogs. (<https://www.britishcouncil.org>)

Learners depend on paperback dictionaries for learning the meaning of difficult words; find the meaning of difficult words, usage and synonyms. Learners feel tiresome and neglect to refer the dictionary. The situation has been changed. With the introduction of online dictionaries, learners feel comfortable and use it speedily to know the meaning of the

difficult words. It helps the learner to enhance vocabulary. Some of the online dictionaries are Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary, Cambridge Advanced Learners Dictionary.

Mobile learning can be divided into mobility of technology, mobility of learner, mobility of learning. (Ramya Gangaiamaran & Madhumathi Pasupathi -Review on use of Mobile Apps for Language Learning- International Journal of Applied Engineering Research – Volume 12 (2017)

Audio books are important source for improving listening skills. The audio books are available on all smart phones. Learners are encouraged to listen to audio books which are available in audio format. These audio books are great source of improving pronunciation.

Swayam Courses are introduced to enhance the knowledge of learners. These courses are meant to study online. They are convenient to learn at their own pace. In addition to their regular courses students can opt swayam courses. At present majority of the students join in these online courses. These courses help not only to gain certificate but also improve English language.

The courses hosted on SWAYAM are in 4 quadrants – (1) video lecture, (2) specially prepared reading material that can be downloaded/printed (3) self-assessment tests through tests and quizzes and (4) an online discussion forum for clearing the doubts. Steps have been taken to enrich the learning experience by using audio-video and multi-media and state of the art pedagogy / technology. In order to ensure best quality content are produced and delivered, nine National Coordinators have been appointed. (<https://swayam.gov.in/about>)

Conclusion:

Many language apps are available for improving language. Many Apps are developed as per the needs of the regional learners to develop English language. Apps are user friendly. All language items are included immediate feedback is given to improve the language. Some of the online apps that are meant for developing English are: The Hindu Vocabulary Builder, STEP, Hello English, Word Association, Vocab Junkie, Mind the Gap, Tandam and Mango.

Mobiles are to be used to develop English among the youth. It should be used in a positive way. It is the need of hour to realize them to use it in a constructive manner to develop their language skills. Students are encouraged to use the best possible ways to develop their language skills using mobile phones.

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